

SELF-HEALING COMPOSITES: IN-SITU REPAIR SOLUTIONS?

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ABSTRACT

Realising self-healing composites in a commercial environment remains a challenge for the transport sector. Herein, this research considers the design envelope and the implications of embedding self-healing agents into commercially relevant fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite applications. A novel epoxy resin containing reversible bondable Diels-Alder structures was developed and implemented into bulk polymer tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) and FRP double cantilever beam (DCB) test specimens to evaluate the recovery of mechanical performance. Fractured test specimens were exposed to 150 °C for a short duration (5 minutes) to facilitate the polymer reconfiguration process. Mode I testing highlighted a combined adhesive and cohesive fracture mechanisms depending on the self-healing material integration method. Healing efficiency values of >50% resulted for the recovery of fracture toughness (K_{Ic}), after the first and subsequent second and third healing cycles.

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of self-healing materials has been an active research area of interest for many international researchers since the early 2000's [1-4]. Although significant developments have been made to demonstrate the structural performance of existing known chemistries (i.e. epoxy-based [5], thermoplastic [6] etc.) as 'self-healing agents' in coupon test specimens, few resources have been placed to evaluate and modify these self-healing systems for industrially relevant applications [7]. The European Commission Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) funded consortium project HIPOCRATES, therefore, aims to develop and demonstrate a self-healing functionality in an industrially relevant high performing fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite demonstrator concept. Fundamental to achieving effective technology integration is healing agent locality, performance and processability.

To put this grand challenge into context the underlying issue of damage in FRP composites needs to be assessed. Internal microscopic damage is ubiquitous in composites that have been subjected to damage, whether this be during the manufacturing process (i.e. via thermal stresses), from machining (i.e. drilling holes for bolted joints), during component assembly or ultimately from in-service loading. Damage is often undetectable from the composite surface and can lead to expensive, time-consuming and not always relevant non-destructive test (NDT) methodologies being employed [8]. Incorporating an in-situ repair solution that can be activated after each of these individual processes could, in the first instance, have a significant impact on reducing composite component scrappage rates, post-manufacture repairs and increase the time period for non-destructive testing (NDT) inspection.

Therefore, the first research output from this project considers the development and implementation of an intrinsic self-healing material, whereby no additional reactive components need to be added once initially synthesised, in order to facilitate self-healing (i.e. unlike the case for microencapsulated or vascularised healing agents) [9,10]. This intrinsic approach was adopted to

address small-scale damage (i.e. cracks of <2 mm) to ultimately be tailored towards certain areas of high stress concentration, such as ply-drops, stringer run-outs and machined holes. The tailorability of a self-healing system is further considered in Figure 1 by way of a roadmap. Herein, damage prone areas, types of damage and materials employed are expanded upon to highlight the key challenges. Namely these consider the material processing conditions, self-healing agent reactivity, quantities, delivery and ultimately mechanical performance.

Achieving a high recovery of mechanical performance (i.e. <50%) is key to justifying the added benefit of adding in a self-healing functionality, without imposing significant reductions to the host matrix material properties. Therefore, this research specifically targets a specific self-healing chemistry that consists of epoxy-amine polymers containing Diels-Alder based thermo-reversible bonds and/or epoxy resin healing agents [11]. The thermally activated Diels-Alder reaction in this case facilitates the reorganisation of so-called ‘fractured’ components to provide the restoration of mechanical properties. Evaluation of this material in bulk polymer and FRP composite test specimens provides the initial proof of concept study, before incorporating into more dynamic and higher demanding applications. The Diels-Alder reaction (Figure 2) that proceeds on the basis of electron transfer has previously been studied by Peterson et al. [12] in the context of self-healing polymers. However, in this study a microencapsulated delivery mechanism was employed. Microencapsulated reagents pose additional restrictions on processing conditions, stability and reagent mixing, all factors that can adversely affect self-healing performance. In this paper, a proof of concept study is presented that outlines the performance of developed Diels-Alder self-healing agents in structural epoxy-based materials.

Figure 1: A roadmap highlighting the self-healing composite development process.

Figure 2: Diels-Alder thermo-reversible reaction

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) test specimens

Silicone moulds, used for casting the TDCB geometry, were formed by pouring RTV 2005 silicone potting compound (RS Components), mixed with 0.1 wt% CAA28 catalyst, into computer numerically controlled (CNC) machined aluminium moulds (Figure 3). Two main TDCB geometry moulds were clamped between aluminium plates and a degassed mixture of 100 parts EPON 828 with 12 parts curing agent DETA was poured into the closed mould and left to cure for 24 hours at ambient temperature and 24 hours at 40 °C [13]. The grooved region was removed using a water-cooled diamond grit saw in thin trench specimens. The Diels-Alder polymer was formed into the main TDCB geometry using a heat gun at 150 °C for < 5 minutes (Figure 4). This process was repeated on both sides of the test specimen. Thin film specimens were manufactured by warming the TDCB main geometry above its glass transition temperature (T_g) value, cutting the grooved trench with a multi-purpose knife and depositing Diels-Alder polymer onto the separated surfaces. The geometry of the TDCB main was retained by reforming test specimens into silicone moulds.

Figure 3: TDCB mould making and test specimen casting process.

Figure 4: (a) A representative example of a thin trench TDCB test specimen, (b) Thin trench feature in TDCB, (c) A representative example of a thin film TDCB test specimen, (d) Thin film feature in TDCB.

2.2. Double cantilever beam test specimens

Carbon/epoxy (SE70, Gurit) unidirectional (UD) plates (160 mm x 150 mm x 4.0 mm) were manufactured using hand lay-up (18 ply) and sealed on an aluminium tool plate under a vacuum of 660-710 mmHg. Cure was undertaken according to the manufacturer's recommendations of 100 °C for 100 minutes under a continuous vacuum in a program controlled oven. The Diels-Alder structural polymer was added into the mid-plane region. Release film (15 µm thickness) was placed from the laminate edge to 5 mm before the start of the inserted polymer region. Cured composite plates were then cut into DCB coupon specimens using a water-cooled diamond grit saw (140 mm x 20 mm x 4.0 mm). Piano hinges were bonded in place using Araldite 2015 adhesive onto grit-blasted surfaces as preparation for mechanical testing (Figure 5).

Figure 5: CFRP double cantilever beam (DCB) Mode I test specimen geometry [14]. Note: all dimensions in mm.

2.3. Test and self-healing protocols

TDCB:

Self-healing performance was assessed using a modified epoxy-based TDCB test specimen arrangement containing a shortened grooved trench section (SCT) [13]. This section consists of the functionally active self-healing Diels-Alder polymer. This arrangement was chosen to control and constrain crack propagation to the central ‘self-healing region’ in order to facilitate self-healing in fractured test specimens. A sharp razor blade was used to precrack cured samples prior to being pin-loaded on an Instron 3343 1 kN load cell. Testing proceeded at a displacement rate of $5 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and test specimens were cracked along the complete SCT length. Fractured specimens were healed by heating to $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for five minutes in a temperature controlled oven. This method was subsequently repeated a further two times to assess multiple healing potential.

Healing performance (η) was calculated from the first failure of initial (P_{Initial}) and healed (P_{Healed}) load values as obtained from mechanical testing (Equation 1). The specific tapered profile of the test specimen geometry results in the fracture toughness being equivalent to the applied load (i.e. $K_{Ic} = P$) [15].

$$\eta = (P_{\text{Initial}} / P_{\text{Healed}}) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

DCB:

Double cantilever beam (DCB) carbon composite test specimens fixed via attached piano hinges were loaded at a displacement rate of 3 mm/min in accordance with ASTM 5528-01 [14], using an Instron 3343 fitted with a 1 kN load cell to initiate and propagate Mode I crack opening. Cracks were propagated for 50 mm from the point of initiation and the crack length recorded with a video camera. Initiated cracks were directed to the self-healing Diels-Alder region via the interleaved release film, to facilitate the fracture and re-bonding of fracture surfaces to restore mechanical performance. Self-healing DCB test specimens were healed for 5 minutes at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Preliminary healing performance values were taken from failure load values ($P_{Initial}$ and P_{Healed}) as outlined previously in Equation 1. The analysis of fracture toughness constitutes towards ongoing future work.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Self-healing agents based on the Diels-Alder reaction (Figure 2) were synthesised from a combination of multifunctional monomers containing epoxy, amine, furfuryl and maleimide functional groups, for compatible integration into epoxy-based materials. These self-healing agents were incorporated into epoxy-based bulk polymer TDCB and carbon FRP DCB test specimens to evaluate the recovery of mechanical performance after fracture has occurred. In both cases the healing mechanism was thermally activated by heating at 150 °C for 5 minutes. The following sections outline the results obtained from mechanical testing.

3.1 Bulk polymer testing in TDCB test specimens

Two configurations of self-healing TDCB test specimens were synthesised in order to evaluate the fracture behaviour at the Diels-Alder – epoxy resin interface. The first configuration, thin trench, considered fracture through the Diels-Alder self-healing polymer by introducing a precrack. This was observed in the load-displacement plot as the first failure at ~0.3mm displacement, subsequent fracture resulted in the crack jumping to the Diels-Alder – epoxy resin interface. This behaviour is visualised in Figure 4 (b). Healing results were, therefore, calculated using the load values from first failure. From this proof of concept study full recovery of fracture toughness (i.e. self-healing of at least 100%) was achieved after three healing cycles (Table 1). These results suggest that the Diels-Alder thermo-reversible reaction that takes place during the healing process is successful in realigning and reforming fractured bonds to re-join fracture surfaces together. This ensures that load can effectively be transferred through the test specimen geometry, once the healing process has completed.

The second configuration utilised a thin film arrangement. This was selected to closely mimic the integration of this self-healing Diels-Alder polymer into FRP composite test specimens. It is in FRP composite materials where space for integrating healing agents is at a premium and where minimum quantities are required to minimise the potential of added mass. Despite the significant reduction in trench thickness from 3 mm to 200 μm for thin trench and thin film test specimens, the initial failure load values are shown to be comparable. This result shows the potential for integrating this self-healing material into FRP DCB specimens using a significantly reduced quantity of self-healing material. The recovery of mechanical performance was additionally shown to exceed 100% in thin film test specimens after three healing cycles (Figure 6 (b)).

Figure 6: (a) A representative load-displacement plot for the Diels-Alder pre-polymer thin trench system, (b) A representative load-displacement plot for the Diels-Alder pre-polymer thin film system. Healing was performed at 150 °C for 5 minutes.

Designation	Healing Efficiency [%]		
	1 st Heal	2 nd Heal	3 rd Heal
Diels-Alder thin trench	125	100	95
Diels-Alder thin film	150	110	110

Table 1: Healing efficiency values from TDCB Diels-Alder thin film and thin trench test specimens.

3.2 Fibre reinforced polymer testing in DCB test specimens

Self-healing Diels-Alder material was subsequently successfully incorporated into carbon FRP DCB test specimens as a result of the previous TDCB test results. Figure 7 represents the recovery of stiffness after healing has occurred after three healing cycles. This data, therefore, represents an average healing efficiency for load of ~55% (Table 2). An increase in healing efficiency, with respect to the number of healing cycles, suggests a longer healing duration may provide higher healing efficiency values through more effective heat transfer. This work is part of an on-going study. A reduction in healing efficiency was observed in comparison with bulk polymer TDCB testing. This is likely to be attributed to the inclusion of reinforced carbon fibres and reduced volume fraction of host matrix material. However, based on the intense load transfer that static Mode I testing imparts on the self-healing material it is achieving a suitable recovery of mechanical performance, in line with the aims set out in the aforementioned roadmap (Figure 1). Specific application to industrially relevant test specimen geometries will ultimately evaluate the true self-healing efficiency of the Diels-Alder material.

Figure 7: A representative load-displacement plot for a self-healing Diels-Alder DCB test specimen. Healing was performed at 150 °C for 5 minutes.

Designation	Healing Efficiency [%]		
	1 st Heal	2 nd Heal	3 rd Heal
Diels-Alder self-healing DCB	45	55	65

Table 2: Healing efficiency values from DCB Diels-Alder FRP composite test specimens.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A novel Diels-Alder modified cross-linked epoxy polymer component has been developed and implemented into structural epoxy-based materials to demonstrate the potential of repair/healing performance in industrially relevant test features. As an initial proof of concept study, results have shown that a material recovery value of greater than 50% fracture strength has been achieved in a bulk epoxy polymer and a high performance prepreg-based FRP composite material using conventional composite manufacturing techniques. This approach represents a truly positive benefit to industry to aid in the optimisation of composite manufacture, by reducing post-manufacture inspection time and material wastage costs, and also to maximise the longevity of composite components in service.

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